

Think, before you link: Link Rot, eBooks, and digital preservation

A REPORT AND GUIDANCE DOCUMENT

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Executive Summary

It is almost impossible to imagine our lives without the Web. Humanity has come to depend on the Web for so many things: social interaction; commerce, entertainment, news and media, and the production and sharing of knowledge itself. The Web is vast, dynamic, and complex.

The Web is also fragile, forgetful, and frustrating. The Web's structure – from websites to social media accounts, URLs to DOIs, paywalls to user logins - reflects our society's structure. As society ebbs and flows; as businesses start up and fold, as governments rise and fall, or as academic debates are contested and settled (or otherwise), so the Web – and websites - change with it.

This churn so often leads to the phenomenon of link rot: where a link to a resource which was once live and retrievable, suddenly becomes inaccessible ('rotten') to the user. As a result, the content which this link served becomes lost – perhaps indefinitely. There are many factors as to why a link can rot, which this report will explore. However, if the information served from a web link is unique and doesn't exist in another form, then link rot can spell disaster: irreplaceable data can be lost, and associated damage is made to our recorded memory.

Link rot has inevitably woven its way into the book publishing world, and into open access eBook preservation. This has led the digital preservation community to respond, to help protect these important components of intellectual and creative life.

Since 2019, the COPIM project and more recently the Open Book Futures project has addressed this as part of their work to develop, 'a larger and more powerful community-led, mission-driven ecosystem for open access books'; including their digital preservation.¹ Throughout these projects, link rot has persistently been raised as a challenge and this report was commissioned to consider how it could be mitigated.

This Report and Guidance Document has two core objectives:

- Explain the background, causes, and current state on link rot and eBook preservation, to promote wider awareness of this issue amongst key stakeholders:
 - authors
 - publishers
 - collecting repositories (including libraries).
- Provide practical advice on how to guard against link rot and how to handle it where it does occur. This practical advice is designed to be:
 - simple
 - scalable
 - cost-effective

¹ <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/introducing-open-book-futures-a-copim-community-project/release/1> [accessed 25 March 2026]

Owing to the Web's fragility, the Report uses a guiding principle that some loss from link rot is inevitable. A key consideration is: how do we prepare and respond to that? Determining 'acceptable loss' from link rot, and how to proportionately plan against it is a further output.

To prevent link rot, the key recommendations, as laid out in Steps 1 to 5 of Part B of this Report are:

1. Think before you link, and determine acceptable loss
2. Cite to resilient links
3. Describe more, bolster accessibility
4. Archive your URLs
5. Monitor your URLs, enact digital archaeology

PART A – UNDERSTANDING THE PROBLEM SPACE

1 eBooks and their preservation

Since their beginnings in the ‘book player’ software days of the early 1990s, eBooks have become a ubiquitous part of the digital landscape (Kirchhoff & Morrissey, [2013](#), pp.4-5). The intellectual content of eBooks is as infinitely wide-ranging as physical books. Whatever or whichever topic an author, scholar or content creator chooses to write about, eBooks now constitute a recognised, common medium for their expressive output.²

The definition of ‘open access’ eBooks can be open to interpretation but in general these relate to eBooks which are available to read, download and reuse, without required payment or website login. Open access (OA) eBooks, are published under an open licence, very often Creative Commons. Being free to access doesn’t guarantee the publishing process will be free for authors: publishing OA eBooks can invoke Book Processing Charges from publishers: costs range from £5,000 up to as high as £50,000. In response, this has led to the development of a number of Diamond Open Access publishers, such as Open Book Publishers and Open Book Collective, which offer free publications services to authors. However, even if the core text of an OA eBook is licence-free, there may be third party or embedded content within the work, which may not be free to share and/or copy.³ The connections of this to link rot will become clear.

Distinguishable from e-journal articles by their length and chapter structure, what makes eBooks fundamentally different to analogue books is simply that they are digital. Being digital exposes eBooks to classic digital preservation risks: technical obsolescence, file format issues, corruption, poor rights management, malware, organisational change, and so on.⁴

Some of these risks may be offset by the fact that, given these are published works, multiple copies may be kept by multiple libraries or collecting organisations, on different systems at multiple locations across the World. However, fundamentally as eBooks are digital, they will require digital preservation to persist over time. This includes awareness and practical approaches to preserving linked information within books: information which may be fundamental to the book itself.

1.1 The technical boundaries challenge

Before assessing the preservation risks that link rot itself imposes on eBooks, we need to define the technical boundaries of an eBook used in this Report.

² See <https://www.doabooks.org/en> for a snapshot of the sheer scale of how many open access eBooks are currently available for access [accessed 26 March 2026]

³ All taken from <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/research/openresearch/oa/oabooks/> [accessed 27 March 2026]

⁴ For more on digital preservation risks see <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dpeg-home/dpeg-risks> [accessed 27 March 2026]

Defining the technical boundaries of an ‘eBook’ has been a topic of debate for some time. This has grown in focus as technology becomes more complex, and the options for creating and blending content into complex digital objects become more varied and accessible (Kirchhoff & Morrissey, p.4; Bell, [2020](#); Barnes, [2025](#)). Embedded, interactive features, data-driven programmatic typeset content, JavaScript-enabled applications, and API-enabled platforms such as Vimeo and Google Maps, can now all be ‘plugged’ into any eBook to enable interoperable user experience, functions, and display. Examples include the award-winning *Feral Atlas* (2020) and *Harlem in Disorder* (2024). There are also growing trends to ‘version’ books over time, which can involve more active involvement (and cost) from publishers in the creation process (Barnes et al., [2023](#), pp.92-99). See *As I Remember It* as an example: originally released, but iterated over time (Paul, [2019](#)).

Such innovation is indicative of creative and societal evolution. But is it legitimate even to consider such works as ‘eBooks’? Many of these features simply cannot be ‘printed’. Are these new creations simply just ‘websites’, ‘web publications’, ‘digital publications’ or even just ‘databases’?⁵

Furthermore, the more complex any digital object is the more difficult it will be to preserve. By their tight coupling to the Web, software dependencies, and user interactions, complex eBooks are highly vulnerable to change, obsolescence and link rot. This risk – web content which is not easily archivable - is well documented in the DPC Bit List (DPC, [2025](#), pp.23-25). We’ll look at this in more detail shortly, but in recent conversation, Neil Jefferies, Executive Director of the Open Preservation Foundation asserted that, ‘if it’s reliant on the Web, then it’s a website.’⁶

Such considerations are very important: if complex eBooks are to be preserved, their form will greatly influence the approach to this work.

This is not to say that these sorts of publications are impossible to preserve, and notable recent initiatives have sought to tackle this challenge. The 2025 Guidelines for Preservability in New Forms of Scholarship, sets out superb practical steps that eBook stakeholders – especially publishers – may follow to support the preservation of complex digital publications (Greenberg et al. [2025](#)). The recent ‘Practice Research Voices’ project from University of Westminster has a similar focus on diffuse digital objects (Ranger, [2022](#)). Impressively, services are already operating to tackle this new preservation challenge. The digital publication preservation service at Stanford University Press (SUP) exists to capture, preserve and make available high-fidelity copies of their digital publications within 3 years of their publication, and ideally within the first 6 months. This includes highly complex publications, and the Press has worked to develop cutting edge advice to authors, and preservation workflows that combine web archiving, comprehensive documentation, and digital accessioning.

The way in which Stanford collects these types of publications illustrates the preservation challenge. Publications can be collected, assembled and made available in the SUP web archive, via the expertise and diligence of curatorial staff. Beyond this convenient online mode of access, users can use the Stanford Digital Repository to gain access to the separate ‘parts’ which make up any

⁵ At a recent Bodleian Open Scholarship webinar, experienced publishing expert Rupert Gatti even confessed he was unsure what constituted a book anymore. Bodleian Open Scholarship webinar, 13 January 2026. <https://zenodo.org/records/18350010> [accessed 27 April 2026]

⁶ Jefferies, N., personal conversation, 9 January 2026

publication and attempt to reassemble and interpret this independently themselves. However, as Jasmine Mulliken, who leads on this work, highlights, these disparate collections of digital parts can often seem similar to, ‘Frankenstein’s monster awaiting assembly’, making documentation and attending re-installation instructions a compulsory part of the full repository collection (Mulliken, speaking at DPC event, ‘Preserving eBooks: where are we now?’, [2026](#); Stanford University Press, [2025](#)).

These projects represent the bleeding edge of eBook and digital publication preservation – possibly coined as the ‘preservation of interoperability’? However, they also represent complex workflows and well-resourced models that would be challenging to scale and roll out to the wider eBook community, especially small, scholar-led presses: the focus of OBF.

For this reasoning, and to keep to this Report’s principle of simple, scalable and cost-effective guidance, our focus is on a simpler technical model for the eBook:

Figure 1: ‘Simple’ eBook technical structure and main components. The dashed red circle indicates where link rot is most likely to occur.

Further details on these components are as follows:

Component Name	Format and typical hosting (i.e. where it normally is stored)
Core text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Format: PDF, EPUB, Word, XML, HTML Host: Local
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Format: ONIX, MARC Host: Local
Embedded content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Format: typically AV (JPEG, WAV, MP4, FLAC etc)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host: Local (but can vary)
Outbound links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Format: typically text, AV, script etc. • Host: external, served via http

The word ‘simple’ is used very loosely(!), as evidently many layers of complexity could permeate in any of this model’s components. For example, metadata may be hosted externally in a separate system and linked to the eBook, embedded AV may be playable on an external web platform etc. There are many, many unusual combinations of doing things on the Web, which would be impossible to advise on in every instance.

However, the ‘simple’ eBook definition allows us to consider practical preservation actions against link rot which will address a reasonably self-contained unit. It is also a conceptual unit which can be more easily recognised, transferred and managed between stakeholder parties (authors, publishers, repositories).

For more complex use cases, readers should refer to the resources cited above. It is assumed that that eBook preservation practice across ‘simple’ and ‘complex’ object models will merge over time, as tools, workloads, awareness and knowledge matures. For the meantime, and for practical purposes, we stick to our thread of understanding how to prevent link rot within ‘simple’ eBooks.

2 Link rot

Before looking at the damaging effect of link rot, let’s firstly understand how linked information is shared through the web.

2.1 How hyperlinks work

Since its invention in 1994, the Web has become the *de facto* source of information for humanity. Whilst there has been a steady pattern of change in software, website design, and applications on the Web, strikingly, the underlying technical framework for how web content is hosted and shared has largely stayed the same, a testament to its design.

All websites on the Web are hosted by a server (hosting computer), which will be linked to the Internet via an Internet Protocol number (a combination of numbers e.g. 81.97.251.146). These numeric codes are not human-friendly, and so the international Domain Name System (DNS) was created to allow websites to be named and indexed in a more memorable way, via Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) e.g. <https://www.gov.uk/>, <https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/>, <https://copim.pubpub.org/open-book-futures-project>. URLs are a form of Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). URIs are used to name anything you can find online, whilst URLs point to the *location* on the Web of where that resource can be found. As link rot is ultimately about a breakage in a user’s request to access information from a certain Web location, URLs are particularly key in this Report.

Dozens of servers may sit behind any one of these websites, each with their own unique IP address. However, the entity binding this content together – the website – is identifiable to users (and their

web browser software) as the URL. This makes URLs – the all-important ‘hyperlinks’ - essential to human and machine understanding of what is available online.

In very simple terms, when a user seeks to access a website, the following workflow occurs:

- 1) The user uses their web ‘client’ (e.g. computer, phone, tablet etc.) to enter the URL of the website they wish to access. Normally browser software (e.g. MS Edge, Chrome, Firefox etc.) is used for this.
- 2) The browser will visit that URL, which will be hosted by a ‘server’ somewhere within the Web.
- 3) If found, the browser will request a copy of the information at that URL to be transferred via HTTP/HTTPS protocol language. If successful, the host server will send a “200 OK” message back, and begin delivering the content to the browser.
- 4) The client browser receives the content (e.g. files, images, text) and renders these for the user in accordance with the website’s encoded structure. This code is normally written in HTML, CSS and JavaScript.

Figure 2: simple workflow for requesting information on the Web

This workflow is high-level, and many other technical ‘handshakes’ can often happen for content to render accurately in the browser (Mozilla, [2026](#)). This does however create a dependency on the URL to remain stable, unaltered, and reliable ‘connective tissue’ for Web access.

In very simple terms, every single URL is made up of two parts:

- 1) the domain from where the content 'lives', owned and controlled by a separate authority.
- 2) the resource or file available from that URL.

This is expressed in the following example:

<https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/connect/>

Orange text: the identity of the authority for this URL (domain).

Blue text: the contact details made available by this authority, via this URL (resource).

As users to this website, or any website for that matter, we have no control over what the authority chooses to do with this domain. It may be appropriate to assume that an institution such as Lancaster University will exist for a long time, and that, by association, so will this website URL. But this can never be guaranteed.

Overall, this can lead to the Web, or at least URLs, becoming fragile, and potentially very frustrating. Let's then consider why and how links rot.

2.2 What is link rot?

In 1998, the founder of the Web, Sir Tim Berners-Lee prophetically wrote:

What makes a cool URI? (or URL)

A cool URI is one which does not change.

What sorts of URL change?

URIs don't change: people change them. (Berners-Lee, [1998](#))

Despite significant development of technology since then, this mantra is still useful for addressing a key question in this Report: why do links break?

When a hyperlink breaks, it means that when a user client attempts to access that information via its URL, they will receive an error message indicating that the information is not available. As described in our text box in the previous section, the authority to the website has moved or changed the location of that resource, and now we can't access it from that original location. 'Link rot' has occurred.

A similar, but very different conclusion to the workflow illustrated in Figure 2 will happen:

- 1) The user uses their web 'client' (e.g. computer, phone, tablet etc.) to enter the URL of the website they wish to access.
- 2) The browser will visit that URL, which will be hosted by a 'server' somewhere within the Web.
- 3) However, the resource at that location is not found. rather than a '200 OK' HTTP response message, the client (and frustrated user) will instead receive a message to indicate the information at that URL cannot be found.
- 4) Error messages can range from:
 - '204 No Content' found message
 - '400 Bad Request' (request is in a format which the server doesn't understand, or has errors)
 - '503 Service Unavailable' (issue with host server)
 - '404 Not Found' is perhaps the most infamous
 - For more commentary see Chapekis et al., [2024](#)
- 5) If found, the browser will request a copy of the information at that URL to be transferred via HTTP/HTTPS protocol language. If successful, the host server will send a "200 OK" message back and begin delivering the content to the browser.
- 6) The client browser receives the content (e.g. files, images, text) and renders these for the user in accordance with the website's encoded structure. This code is normally written in HTML, CSS and JavaScript.

Figure 3: Simple workflow for broken links

Figure 4: 404 broken link from the US White House website⁷

Whether this is temporary outage, or something more permanent, is often very difficult to discern – and frustrating to the user. Sometimes there are clues. For example, a 503 error normally means a temporary server issue that may be restored, and sometimes 404 error messages can be termed as ‘soft’ in that the DNS lookup failed due to networking issue, rather than a problem at the URL itself. Checking back is sometimes worthwhile, but even a temporary block can disillusion the user, as noted by Berners-Lee long ago,

‘When someone follows a link and it breaks, they generally lose confidence in the owner of the server. They are also frustrated – emotionally and practically from accomplishing their goal.’ (Berners-Lee, [1998](#))

Link rot can manifest in another, more complicated way. ‘Content drift’ refers to a situation where an original URL may stay the same, but the content within it changes.⁸ Without any change control or obvious audit function, a user arriving at a URL for the first time is oblivious to any changes. In its worst form, websites can be disregarded by their owner, and become subject to ‘cyber-squatting’: where the URL is re-sold and re-purposed by another owner, sometimes for nefarious purposes. Public sector website links which lapse their domain licence are prone to this threat, given that these

⁷ This URL, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/news/releases/2003/05/20030501-15.html>, originally took clients to a transcript of President George W. Bush’s now-infamous “Mission Accomplished” press release during the 2003 Iraq War. The live page was subsequently removed, and only versions of the original exist in the Internet Archive, including an [earlier](#) and [later](#) version. Example taken from DHSR Blog, ‘Keynote at Pacific Neighbourhood Consortium’ (2017) available at <https://blog.dshr.org/2017/11/keynote-at-pacific-neighborhood.html> [accessed 30/03/2026]

⁸ The President Bush e.g. cited above is an example of content drift.

websites likely attracted user traffic in the past, and could attract profitable, likely unsolicited traffic to new, often inappropriate content.

This interferes with all sorts of online content, including eBooks. For example: the screenshot below is taken from [Medbh McGuckian: The Poetics of Exemplarity](#), by Shane Alcobia-Murphy, an OA eBook published in 2012. The links in the footer of page 73 of this eBook were cited at the time of the book's publication but have been subject to link rot in the intervening years.

Figure 5: Screenshot from online page of Open Access eBook, *Medbh McGuckian: The Poetics of Exemplarity* (Alcobia-Murphy, 2012)

Opening the link to the page entitled, 'A Hell Bird', presumably a poem and available at a website called <https://www.argotistonline.co.uk/>, sadly now leads to gambling content on the same URL:

Figure 6: screenshot showing where original URL for a former poetry website now leads to gambling content - evidence of 'cyber squatting'

Evidently, the URL licence for the Argotist Online domain URL, [argotistonline.co.uk](https://www.argotistonline.co.uk), became available for resale at some point between 2012 and now, and was purchased to point users to this new, unrelated content.⁹ With this clean break to the original content, link rot has occurred and the original online content on [argotistonline.co.uk](https://www.argotistonline.co.uk) is practically irrecoverable.

2.3 Why does link rot happen?

We have touched on some of the causes of link rot, but the root cause is simply that content on the Web is directly connected to *us*. As we evolve as a society, as governments rise and fall, as businesses come and go, as trends in culture, fashion, sport and hobbies wax and wane, so websites start and end. Some of the main catalysts for link rot are laid out in figure 7:

⁹ A similar example includes the former professional information governance website, 'Information Governance 101', which now points to a [Vietnamese gambling site](#). [accessed 10 April 2026]

Figure 7: high-level causes of link rot¹⁰

2.4 The evidence over time

We have determined so far that the Web and URLs are fragile and often frustrating. But to indulge in further alliteration, how ‘forgetful’ is the Web?

Despite Tim Berners-Lee’s plea to create ‘Cool URIs’ which don’t die, link rot has been around for a long time, and the Web appears very forgetful indeed. This is especially the case for older content.

Headlines from research into this topic include:

- In 2013, Maureen Pennock in her DPC Technology Watch Report reported that the average lifespan of a webpage was between 44 and 100 days. (Pennock, [2013](#), p3.)
- As we have observed, URLs are a form of a URI, but assumptions of transience surrounding these digital information identifiers is observed within 2010 UK Government advice on URI design that ‘public sector URI sets that are promoted for re-use should be designed to last for at least [a paltry] 10 years.’ (UK Cabinet Office, [2010](#))

¹⁰ For examples see:

Poorly planned website renewal: <https://www.politifact.com/article/2022/mar/17/how-broken-urls-helped-fuel-unfounded-conspiracy-t/>

Past geopolitical upheaval: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1461444816643790> - article documenting the loss of the web domain of the former Yugoslavia (.yu) which was deleted in 2010

Industrial action: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3717867.3717873>

Cyber threat: <https://dl-acm-org.ezproxy1.lib.gla.ac.uk/doi/10.1145/3589334.3645510>

Third party platform dependency: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-47610936> [all accessed 30 March 2026]

- More recently, researchers from Pew Research recorded that 25% of all web pages dating between 2013 and 2023 were no longer accessible, with older content especially affected. (Chapekis et al., [2024](#))
- Even more recently, in 2025 Michael L. Nelson from Old Dominion University shared during a DPC event that the median lifespan of a URL is now 2.3 years, with short URLs having a much greater chance of survival than links with long paths and multiple slashes. (Nelson, [2025](#))

Our suspected characteristics of the Web - fragility, forgetfulness, and user frustration - seem clear. What about the online scholarly record? The COPIM and OBF projects had sought to, ‘support communities of scholars, small-to-medium-sized publishers, not-for-profit infrastructure providers and scholarly libraries, enabling community-led open access book publishing in all its plurality to play a significant role in the future of academic books’. This particular category of information seems relevant here, so what is the picture? Sadly, it’s very similar:

- A 2014 study found that over the course of the 2000s, Science, Technology and Medical academic journal articles steadily included more and more URL references, but that 70-80% of articles dated 2005-2012 contained link rot, reducing to 20% for 2009-2012 (though likely worse now with the passage of time). (Klein et al., [2014](#))
- A 2015 analysis noted that 36% of a sample of 193,955 URLs found in a corpus of Elsevier journals were rotten, with further evidence that older content and longer links was more prone to rot. (Zhou et al., [2015](#))
- More recently, a 2021 study rather shockingly uncovered that 174 Open Access journals dating from 2000 to 2019 had simply vanished from the Web, suggesting serious digital preservation issues. (Laakso et al., [2021](#))
- This theme of web data loss was further evidenced in 2025, where over 20% of a large analysis of online repositories of scholarly information dated 2001 onwards, were proven to be “dead” or rotten, and to make matters worse scholars at time of publication were citing references that were already rotten – a challenge to the credibility of the research itself. [Macgregor and Davidson, [2026](#)]
- Perhaps more tenuously, but resiliently popular, Wikipedia relies on outbound links for external information, but c.11% of these links are broken as at 2024. (Chapekis et al., [2024](#), p.9)

The key takeaway therefore is that the Web *is* fragile, *is* forgetful, *is* frustrating – even when authoritative scholarly publications are in scope.

To think of a physical analogy, link rot is similar to a missing book on the Library shelf that may be the key resource needed for a user enquiry. Only it’s much more common, much harder to detect, and probably not possible to solve through an inter-library loan. Once information disappears from the Web, unless it’s archived, it’s likely not coming back.

2.5 Digital preservation response

The digital preservation community has been alert to the danger of link rot for decades, and many web archiving efforts have been established to offset the risk. At the highest level, the web archiving workflow is as follows:

Figure 8: high level web archiving workflow

- Capture: websites which are selected for archiving are visited by web crawler software (e.g. Heritrix, Brozzler). The web crawler navigates around the website's links structure, copying content as it goes, to create a time-stamped 'capture' of how the site looked at that moment in time.
- Quality assurance: often issues to do with missing content and poor replay for access are handled at this step, through manual and automated processing.
- Replay: archived content is made available for user access via replay software e.g. OpenWayBack, PY-WB.

Building from this core model are established and successful web archiving programmes, run by collecting organisations such as the Internet Archive, and national libraries and archives across the Globe. Reducing link rot has been a stated goal of these organisations for years, (as of 2025, the Internet Archive is believed to have repaired over 23 million broken links) and it is sobering to consider where we would be without these collections (Rossi, [2013](#)). eLegal Deposit legislation has been a powerful catalyst for enabling the development of national domain web archiving across the World (although access itself may be restricted to onsite users), and global networks such as the International Internet Preservation Consortium (IIPC) and DPC exist to support and disseminate community knowledge in this space.¹¹

Open source and commercial software-as-a-service offerings have emerged in the last few decades, enabling smaller organisations to capture, preserve, and make available web content important to them, before this disappears from the live web. Web crawlers such as Heritrix, Browsertrix and Brozzler, and replay software such as Py-WB and OpenWayBack are now part of the global digital

¹¹ For a listing of large-scale web archiving programmes see 'IIPC Members' available at <https://netpreserve.org/about-us/members/> [accessed 01 April 2026]

preservation infrastructure.¹² Powerfully, web archiving has also enabled many grassroots initiatives to capture a record of voices within our community who have historically been poorly represented within official records.¹³

The recognised tools and workflows for web archiving are reasonably well established – though often challenging to resource. Furthermore, internationally agreed preservation file formats exist which allow for the preservation of a website’s content *and* look and feel.¹⁴

Encouragingly, as more and more users encounter link rot (as the Web ages indefinitely) and as more users encounter web *archive* content, purposefully or otherwise, media and investigative attention is growing around the unique value of these collections (Freeland, [2026](#)).

2.6 Challenges to web archiving

Whilst greater awareness can be reputationally positive to web archives, it can also make them more prominent targets. This is evidenced by recent visceral attacks on web archives and their home institutions, none more so than the British Library, keeper of the UK Web Archive. Two and a half years on from the 2023 cyberattack, the UK Web Archive is still offline and may be so for some months yet (Bowie, [2025](#)). If a user encounters a broken link from the UK Web Archive, it would be fairly easy to discern why this may be the case through a Google search. But if smaller, lower-profile web archives were to suffer the same fate, much more user uncertainty and frustration could arise.

Another challenge can relate to how websites are designed and built. The following, common features can often create technical challenges to conventional web archiving approaches:

- Interactive Content – this is any content which requires a user’s input, including search and lookup functionality via server-side processing.
- Dynamically generated content and scripts e.g. Javascript, AJAX
- Links inside documents (such as PDF, MS Word or Excel).
- Content which requires a login.
- Flash content (a now extinct technology, but common in older websites for displaying AV content – see the DPC *Bit List* pp.162-165, DPC, [2025](#)).
- Embedded content, including maps and social media such as YouTube videos – these videos are often stored and streamed as chunks, which can easily upset the crawl process.
- http POST – this function serves content by sending data to a server to create/update a resource. This data-driven interaction can lead the web crawler to become confused and fail.

¹² The community-maintained ‘Awesome Web Archiving’ list is the best source for information and links to the latest web archiving tools and services: <https://github.com/iipc/awesome-web-archiving> [accessed 27 April 2026]

¹³ Examples here include Documenting the Now and the Community Webs programme. For information see <https://web.archive.org/web/20260419232249/https://www.docnow.io/> and <https://web.archive.org/web/20250201211231/https://communitywebs.archive-it.org/collection-development/> [both accessed 27 April 2026]

¹⁴ See link to the ‘Awesome Web Archiving list’ above.

HTTP GET is a much better option, being a simpler protocol for receiving information straight from a URL.

These technical challenges can and do change all the time. As the Web constantly evolves, web archiving technology must evolve too (crawlers, replay, QA etc.), but this can challenge the scalability and sustainability of this work.¹⁵ This can also create uncertainty for planning and quality metrics: it can still be challenging for web archivists to predict how a web crawl will go, such is the complexity of modern sites, and the results can often be disappointing. If website design is a factor, there is little that can be done in retrospect, leading Lynn Bruce, former Web Archivist at National Records of Scotland, to observe, ‘sometimes you just get what you get.’¹⁶

Furthermore, current web archiving models cater primarily to the preservation of ‘traditional’, static websites, which require little server-side processes and dynamic features for user customisation. Of course, the Web consists of so much more than that.

Social media and hosted AV content are examples. The history of archiving social media has been mixed – in the 2010s programmes existed to archive Twitter at scale, and innovative tools were produced to capture content from platforms such as YouTube, Tumblr and Sina Weibo. (Ostberg, [2017](#))¹⁷ Whilst ‘DIY’ options persist for users to download copies of their own content from social media platforms (Jackson, [2025](#); Wright, [2021](#)), scalable social media archiving has become extremely challenging. Changes to how platforms make their content available, coupled with assertive Terms and Conditions, makes archiving risky, inconsistent, and legally complex.

It should also be noted that web archives will only *ever* preserve a proportion of the Web (Zhou et al., [2015](#), p.234; MacGregor & Davidson, [2026](#), p.15; Sawood, A. & Graham, M. [2025](#)) (Even if crawlers were able to access content behind paywalled content and logins, technical challenges such as server-side scripted content and poor web design are barriers to successful capture and replay of content. This ‘partial’ archive is invaluable but will always have this constraint.

Another challenge is simply sustaining such work. Many initiatives specifically established to tackle link rot have fallen by the wayside very recently, notably the ‘Memento Time Travel’ and ‘Robust Links’ services.¹⁸ Whilst elements of these services still exist as open source tools and associated

¹⁵ For example, Conifer was a hosted service that enabled customers to capture content from the Web. Changes in how web archiving technology has had to adapt to more complex websites, and a lack of successful integration options with the Conifer platform, was one of the factors in the ongoing close-down of this web archiving service platform. Conifer, ‘Announcement to Conifer Users: “Twilight” Plans and Our Continued Commitment to Web Preservation’, available at <https://blog.conifer.rhizome.org/2025/12/15/twilight-announcement.html> [accessed 01 April 2026]

¹⁶ Lynn Bruce personal conversation, 17 December 2025.

¹⁷ For example, see Social Feed Manager and YouTube-DL applications, available at <https://gwu-libraries.github.io/sfm-ui/> and <https://github.com/ytdl-org/youtube-dl> respectively [both accessed 27 April 2026].

LOC Twitter Archive, YouTube-DL, <https://gwu-libraries.github.io/sfm-ui/>

¹⁸ ‘Memento – Time Travel for the Web’, available at <https://mementoweb.org/about/> [accessed 31 March 2026].

services respectively, it is interesting that web archiving's adaptations to the Web's complexity in recent years has challenged business models of these sorts of enterprises.¹⁹

Focusing our attention again to link rot within eBooks, services and methods have emerged to offset link rot within academic online literature. Perma.cc is a service hosted by Harvard University that caters specifically to tackling link rot within the academic community, offering a means to create 'permanent links' to academic citations, and is offered as a free service to academic libraries.²⁰ There is strong potential here for the eBook preservation case, but it has been noted that whilst perma.cc offers benefits, getting familiar with its workflow and administration can still be resource intensive (Lake, 2025).

Furthermore, several options for persistent identifiers (PIDs) for web content are also available to scholars, authors, and content providers – notably DOIs, Handles, and ARKs. It's important to note that nothing on the Web can truly be considered 'permanently' persistent – ultimately all PIDs will be connected to some sort of user, business or organisation, which may eventually fold. There are plenty of myths and scepticism surrounding their usage too, not helped by occasionally large outages owing to human error.²¹ Nevertheless, these provide very useful tools for offsetting link rot, and are explored in the guidance section below.

2.7 The current context: a petri dish for link rot

In many respect the causes of link rot, and the examples cited above follow a familiar risk pattern for digital content: organisational change; technological obsolescence, software lifecycles, and so on.²² However, what sets the Web apart is its ubiquity within modern life. According to the World Bank Group, in 2025, 74% of the World's population – c.6 *billion* people – were using the Internet.²³ This is a lot of users, a lot of websites, and, inevitably, a lot of link rot. This also makes the Web incredibly attractive to commercial interests, leading to constant change and rapid technology lifecycles. This only increases the likelihood of link rot, and raises the barrier to scalable, effective web archiving.

Wider current events across the World also have a negative impact:

- Geopolitical tensions are leading to widespread Internet shutdowns and web content manipulation, as actors seek to control social narratives.

¹⁹ Memento persists as an Internet Request for Comment, available at <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7089> 'Memgator' is a command line tool which allows lookup of relevant archived webpages across the world, using the Memento RFC protocol. <https://github.com/oduwsdl/MemGator> The RobustLinks source code also lives on at <https://github.com/iipc/robustlinks> [all accessed 31 March 2026].

²⁰ <https://perma.cc/> [accessed 27 April 2026]

²¹ In 2015 staff at the US Corporation for National Research Initiatives failed to renew the doi.org domain name causing a global outage to a large proportion of the DOI network. Taken from Barnes & Cole, [2024](#). Uniqueness of DOI can also be a problem (van Gerven Oei, [2025](#)) For a playful primer for 'myths' associated with PIDs, see Kunze, [2018](#). [all accessed 31 March 2026].

²² For further explanations on these general risk patterns see, DPC, [2025](#)

²³ World Bank Group, 'Individuals using the Internet (% of population)' available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.NET.USER.ZS> [accessed 01 April 2026]

- change could be happening on a greater scale, out of sight and beyond reach of web archiving programs.²⁴
- Growing mistrust of government via misinformation and fake news has been greatly worsened by real evidence of explicit and abrupt web content takedown.
 - capturing this content before it is removed adds huge pressure to preservation services.²⁵
- Concerns of a growing ‘centralization’ of the Web, where economic factors lead to domination by large platforms such as Meta, Google, and Netflix for all Web content (Rosenthal, [2018](#)). Archiving content from these platforms is very difficult technically and legally. This could create major blockers to preservation if centralization continues.
- Furthermore, the growth of AI has created two related issues:
 - The huge increase in bots used by AI platforms to capture content from the Web for large language model processes has led many websites to crash and go offline, including cultural heritage collections (Weinberg, [2025](#))
 - To block AI-bots from entering their sites, many website owners are imposing tools such as Cloudflare, that seeks to allow human-users only. Sadly, these blocking measures can also hinder the progress of benevolent bots, including web archive crawlers.

We live in uncertain times. This makes the case for collective, collaborative support to these threats greater than ever. It is heartening to see so much action being taken by the digital preservation community to respond to this set of circumstances. Time will tell whether this ‘petri-dish’ for link rot becomes as damaging as it could be, but we now consider what stakeholders to eBooks can do to offset this within their own publishing and collecting workflows.

3 The impact on eBooks

A link rot risk exists against the website on which an eBook is made available: whether that be a large aggregator site like the Directory of Open Access Books, or individual press websites themselves like the University of Westminster Press. Some of the guidance provided below may be useful in considering the construction of resilient, accessible websites, and there are many resources available to support design thinking (COPIM, [2026](#); [TNA](#); [Bingham](#)). Given that many small-scale publishers

²⁴ The development of the Russian Independent Media Archive illustrates resistance to this. Established to preserve the work of independent journalists in modern Russia, including government-blocked websites. See <https://rima.media/> [accessed 01 April 2026]

²⁵ Nowhere more so than in USA, where data relating to LGBT health, vaccines, and scientific data have been removed since early 2025 due to Presidential administration executive orders. See <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cgkj8gx1vy6o>; <https://www.datarescueproject.org/guest-post-the-world-factbook-is-gone/> Rapid collecting response has been incredibly powerful, and work continues to develop collectives to preserve knowledge from government interference. See <https://nsarchive.gwu.edu/briefing-book/climate-change-transparency-project/2025-09-30/disappearing-data-part-ii-distorted>; <https://www.bbc.co.uk/future/article/20250422-usa-scientists-race-to-save-climate-data-before-its-deleted-by-the-trump-administration>; and <https://works.hcommons.org/records/xd3c5-g7j14> [All accessed 01 April 2026]

rely on online library platforms for their eBook hosting, this will be critical to monitor over time. It is positive to see OBF developing community-owned archiving frameworks as a robust alternative (Barnes et al., [2022](#)).

However, the core threat of link rot to eBooks would appear to be the threat to the integrity, value and trustworthiness of the eBook digital objects themselves, and this is what this Report addresses in particular. But how big a risk is this?

Reflecting on the working model for an eBook set out in section 2.1, and considering the causes, risks, and current circumstances that feed into link rot as described above, it is clear vulnerabilities are very present, especially in relation to eBook embedded content.

eBooks contain rich embedded media to support user access and interaction. This embedded content can be hosted locally 'at source', packaged as an important component of any eBook digital object, and accessible to render from the same source.

However, embedded content can often be pulled into eBooks from external sources via outbound links. This is hardly surprising, given the scale of resource and data available on the Web, and given the huge creative and intellectual threads that go into the production of any one eBook. To suggest any alternative approach to this would be folly, and many eBooks (in the broadest definition) in many ways resemble an artistic output rather than simple textual artefact.

The challenge that this 'reference wrangling' creates for long-term preservation is that for every hyperlink that an author or creator uses to pull external content into their work for added perspective or value, immediately becomes vulnerable to link rot.

Is there anything particular about OA eBooks that feeds into this risk profile? Perhaps the most distinctive element here is the frequently low economic-base that small and scholar-led OA Presses have to work within. This limits overall resilience to change and challenges, and means that resources appropriately have to be focused entirely on the core parts of the publishing workflow – editing, peer review, design, and so on (Barnes et al. [2022](#)). This further emphasises that the guidance provided in this Report must be simple, scalable, cost-effective, and as compatible with existing working practices as possible.

Figure 1 highlighted the aspects of our eBook technical model which are particularly vulnerable to link rot. It is difficult to assert without further quantitative research how many URLs are typically within eBooks in general, never mind OA eBooks specifically. However this challenge has been present for some time, and from the anecdotal research carried out through this study, it is very clear that URLs are staples of the eBook production process (Barnes & Cole, [2024](#)). The link rot risk is real, however it is encouraging that recent research suggested no discernible link between the likelihood of link rot and the open or closed status of an e-journal article (Zhou et al, [2015](#), p.236).

3.1 Key messages for eBook stakeholders

From this background, it is clear that link rot is an issue which is heavily influenced by how websites and web links are used and cited. This places a lot of the success in dealing with link rot at the

creation (i.e. eBook authoring) stage. Authors are perhaps the key stakeholders for preventing link rot within OA eBooks.

However, it is unclear how alert authors are to this – that they are *not* the owners, nor have control of the ongoing lifecycle management of external, linked third party content. The danger is that this lack of awareness, or implicit, but likely misguided trust in external links can create jeopardy to their own intellectual works. If they want their own work and legacy to live on, then this point must be advocated strongly.

There may even be some lasting belief that URLs, or DOIs, are by themselves ever-lasting, and that no further resilience is required. This could tap into common misconceptions as to what constitutes an actual ‘digital archive’ (SAA, [2018](#)).

As we have observed, given that Web links are extremely susceptible to link rot, it is very likely, nay inevitable that at some point in the future history of that eBook, that link will sever, and the content will no longer be accessible. As noted in sections 2.4 to 2.6, the evidence for this is very clear.

It is also the case that there is only one Web – if a URL breaks, then it breaks for everyone. The content itself *may* survive – in a web archive or on an alternative URL. However, when a link breaks, then the original URL route to that content vanishes too, possibly for good.

Broken links, missing content, frustrated users, are some of the practical negative consequences that can occur in the wake of link rot. But there are huge considerations relating to the intellectual properties of eBooks which could also be called into question. If we apply archival principles to this equation, broken links could lead to the questioning or damage to any of the following characteristics of any eBook:

Authenticity	that the content and information contained in the eBook remains trustworthy
Integrity	that the eBook’s content remains accurate and complete
Availability	that the full content (and meaning) of the eBook can be found and rendered
Provenance	That the origin of the eBook is clear and indicates that the content is what it purports to be

Awareness and sharing of these principles may help incentivise authors in this mission to preserve eBooks. Like most things in digital preservation, prevention is easier than cure: risks to digital objects are so much easier to mitigate through good design and sensible technical choices by their creator. As nearly summed up by Karen Hanson from PORTICO, ‘preservation, especially of complex material, is far more difficult when it’s an afterthought’ (Hanson, [2025](#)).

It is hoped that the information outlined above will be useful to publishers and collecting organisations in engaging with authors and creators in this important process. We now turn to considering real practical steps to affect this further.

PART B – BUILDING RESILIENCE AGAINST LINK ROT

The following series of steps provide advice on how to engineer resilience into outbound links within eBooks and in making difficult decisions on which links *must* survive. A description of each step is laid out, following by a checklist for each stakeholder to eBook preservation: authors, publishers, and collecting repositories.

- Step 1 - Think before you link, and determine acceptable loss
- Step 2 – Cite to resilient links
- Step 3 – Describe more, bolster accessibility
- Step 4 – Archive your URLs
- Step 5 – Monitor your URLs, enact digital archaeology

These steps build on excellent recent work already referenced in this paper. However, in keeping with the ethos and principles of the Report, these steps are strictly designed to be:

- simple
- scalable
- cost-effective

Information detail is kept at a reasonable high level, with links to more specific resources and case studies as appropriate. These steps are accurate as at the time of writing, and will change over time, as the Web, web design, and web archiving methods evolve.

To help understand costs and resourcing for each step, a simple cost rating scale is used as an indicator:

- £ - low cost/effort**
- ££ - moderate cost/effort**
- £££ - high cost/effort**

Steps 1-3 can be regarded as the ‘minimal’ steps to mitigate link rot and provide better link resilience within eBooks and are largely related to the ‘creation’ phase for eBooks: where books are written, web links are cited to, and descriptive metadata is assembled.

Steps 4 to 5 could be considered if additional resource were available: especially for links of very high informational value, and are relevant for once an eBook has been published and can be considered ‘in circulation’.

Step 1 - Think before you link, and determine acceptable loss

Potential cost rating: ££

As noted in Part A of this Report the chances of link rot are very high, especially for older web content. Data loss through link rot is inevitable. A difficult but important decision for eBook stakeholders to consider is, what level of link rot could any one eBook withstand?

Given loss is linked to outbound hyperlinks – ***think before you link.***

For authors in particular: do you really need the hyperlink you are referring to? If hyperlinks are needed it may be helpful to frame their use and citation by answering the simple question, *must it survive?*

Information management principles may help frame this further. In the mostly analogue world of the late 1990s, it was determined that roughly 10% of an organization or business’s records could be considered ‘vital’ and worthy of long-term preservation (Kennedy & Schauder, 1998, p.241). Into the 2000s, approximately 5% of all public records generated by the UK Government were transferred to the UK National Archives ([TNA](#)), and modern departmental records management policies still assert this statistic (MOD, [2024](#)).²⁶ It is likely that the rate of acquisitions of digital records into archives has grown recently, due to higher volumes of digital records, and ergonomic challenges in their processing. The point here is that it is normal to work with loss when appraising digital material, and prioritization is key. More recently, environmental concerns have also led professionals to consider exactly what should be selected for archiving, and what should not: given the carbon footprint associated with digital preservation (NDSA, [2026](#); DPC, [2026](#)). To paraphrase Benjamin Goldman, loss in archives is likely, and sometimes, even desirable (Goldman, [2019](#), p.289).

Guidelines for Preservability in New Forms of Scholarship defines this critical information as “core intellectual components: the aspects of a publication that are considered integral to the understanding of it.” This is a very helpful framework for determining acceptable loss, and to take it one step further, authors should consider whether their eBook will continue to be understood by future users – or at the very least the next generation of users - if/when the linked content is no longer available? The authors of eBooks will understand their users better than anyone.

Checklist for authors

- Determine your acceptable loss.
A risk-based approach to determining which links must survive could be useful.
Considerations could include:
 - Consider how long you want the book and its links to last and work back from there – bearing in mind that the average website these days is expected to last 2.3 years.

²⁶ Despite being seemingly small in %, this scale could still be enormous. In 2024 the US Nara Archives and Records Association acquired 463 terabytes of digital records – the equivalent of over 4 trillion individual pieces of paper. NARA, ‘National Archives by the Numbers’, available at <https://www.archives.gov/about/info/national-archives-by-the-numbers> [accessed 01 April 2026]

- Do you really need to link?
 - If you need to link, think in terms of what your users need, and be strategic and selective in what you link to.
 - Consider the sources that you are linking to – are their hosts likely to last for a long time? Remember, URLs are ultimately tied to the fortunes and longevity of their authority.
 - Probable strong hosts with predictable longevity would include government websites, large news agencies, institutions etc.
 - Avoid short-term project websites, draft versions of document, and press releases which will likely change over time.
 - User experience:
 - Why are you linking and what are you expecting users to do with those links?
 - Would the user experience be ruined when links break?
 - Is user experience or evidential value of the book more important? Assess link dependencies against this.
 - Consider the information management loss % above: sometimes loss is ok, and that short-term user experience and user customisation *may be* critical – just remember that this almost certainly will not be preserved.
 - Observe that links and embedded media such as video and media which enhance the current user experience, could create user accessibility problems.
 - Does including the link introduce copyright, ethical and/or legal risk? For example, the terms of conditions of platforms such as YouTube can prohibit sharing.
 - In the eventuality that links in the eBook break:
 - Would user and/or academic trust in the eBook be damaged?
 - Would use and re-use value of the work be undermined?
 - Is the URL in question already archived by a reputable, recognisable, publicly available archive?²⁷
 - Can the content be accessed and used effectively? It is worth testing this to ensure the quality of capture is satisfactory?
- Plan next steps.

Once the links are considered, the **informational value** of the content they host can inform next steps:

 - Is the information that you are linking to critical to user understanding of your text?
 - **If critical** → refer to Step 2: cite accordingly, point to a web archive, and add additional descriptive text with accessibility in mind.
 - **If important but not critical** → refer to Step 2: cite accordingly.
 - **If not critical or important, there are options to consider:**

²⁷ For a listing of openly available web archives, see Appendix A.

- Keep the URL in situ for transparency purposes, but consider whether a 404 message could generate future risk and user frustration
 - If retained in situ, consider including as much descriptive detail of what the content is as you can, remembering that that the link itself will break at some point
 - If the link points to supplementary information, or information which would likely be easily retrievable via a simple Web search – remove it
- Package if you can.

For critical or important content available at outbound links, there is the option of packaging this as separate files and/or metadata within the eBook itself – to be accompanied along with the core text when submitting to a publisher.

 - For example, if linking to a video on an external platform such as YouTube or Vimeo, consider whether the video file could be stored or hosted locally, and submitted as part of your eBook to a publisher. Do carefully consider the copyright and licencing of content in situations like this.
 - The file format in which the information is stored could have a major bearing on its acquisition and long-term preservation.²⁸ This is a large topic, but a useful starting point is checking which formats archives and libraries typically prefer for preservation ([TNA](#), [LOC](#)). OBF has further guidance (Barnes et al., [2023](#), pp.13-50).
 - Reach out to your publisher to understand their preference for file formats and associated metadata.
 - If still in doubt, reach out to community networks such as Thoth, DPC or CLOCKKS for further advice.

Checklist for publishers

- It may be worth approaching these questions in a similar vein
 - when an eBook manuscript arrives for publication, assess the links and ask yourself the questions above.
 - If in doubt, reach out to the author – if you can – to discuss the importance of their links. In this discussion be sure to emphasise the key risks:
 - URLs are prone to loss over time – *at least* 25% will break within a few years.
 - That inserting links in general could create dependencies that may fail.
 - That content of critical value to a book’s understanding should not rely on outbound hyperlinks.

²⁸ File format is defined as “a standard way that information is encoded for storage in a computer file. It tells the computer how to display, print, and process, and save the information.” – think MS Word, Powerpoint, PDF, mp3, HTML, JPEG etc. Definition taken from the DPC ‘Glossary’ available at <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/glossary#F> [accessed 01 April 2026]

- If links are found, go back to the author to determine whether better citation is required → see step 2.

Checklist for collecting repositories

- In addition to the above, it may be worth providing or publishing written guidance to authors and publishers based on the above, to circulate these important messages as widely as possible.

Step 2 – Cite to resilient links

Potential cost rating: £

Having gone through Step 1, it is still very likely that the author will wish to retain some URLs with important or critical content to their eBook. From our discussion above, we know how convenient and powerful linking to external information on the Web can be: this will remain a standard part of the writing process indefinitely.

The next practical advice then is to consider what makes a good link – one which has as little chance of corrupting and rotting over time - and how best to cite to it.

Checklist for authors

What do resilient links look like? Here are some practical pointers when considering which links to use:

- URL links which follow the ‘KISS’ principle – “keep it simple, Stupid”. Longer links with long paths (i.e. many slashes) have a lesser chance of successfully resolving over time and/or being archived (Alkwai et al, 2019, pp.9-11). Further simple tips include:
 - If a URL contains a ‘?’, determine if the text after the ‘?’ is required for the link to load. If it is not, remove to safely trim the link.
 - Avoid URLs which contain unsafe characters (Starr, 2025).
- In support of user accessibility, URLs should ideally be self-describing and unambiguous i.e. it is clear from their text what they relate to.
- To support long-term readability, links should be cited as written in the browser (full web address), rather than the suggested text that modern office software often provides.
 - e.g. use <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/store-evaluate/archives-and-records-management>, not [Archives and Records Management | Data Management](#)
- Content served from links should ideally be in HTML rather than PDF. Information *within* HTML is much easier to find by users and machines, rather than PDF (GOV.UK, 2018; w3c, Robust – principle 4). It will also have a greater chance of being crawled and archived by a web crawler.
- Link to document landing pages, rather than individual documents:
 - e.g. use <https://www.gov.scot/publications/online-safety-taskforce-action-plan-2026-27/>, not

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2026/03/online-safety-taskforce-action-plan-2026-27/documents/online-safety-taskforce-action-plan-2026-27/online-safety-taskforce-action-plan-2026-27/govscot%3Adocument/online-safety-taskforce-action-plan-2026-27.pdf>

- Avoid links which point to paywalled, or login-only content, such as closed network storage areas, social media, closed access journal article etc.
- Internal links within a website should be relative and not use absolute paths. This means that the links are based on the structure of the individual website, and do not depend on accessing an external location where files are held.
- Links to primary sources (e.g. academic or government reports) are better than secondary sources (e.g. news article to the report, tweet).
- Avoid shortened links e.g. bit.ly, TinyURL, given this creates an additional and unnecessary dependency for the link to resolve.
- When dealing with database assets, or information contained within links which may be long or fragile, link to a higher-level URL rather than a link derived from a search.
- Beware unsafe URLs, which could lead to malware or phishing. A good checklist for spotting suspicious links is available here: <https://catonmat.net/safe-urls-101>.
- If they are available, persistent identifiers such as DOI and ARKs have a greater chance of longevity than standard links, and should be selected ahead of URLs – however, do not *assume* these will last indefinitely, for reasons discussed in section 2.5.
- If possible, avoid redirection links for citations: if the original URL still exists, use that.

Adding descriptive detail within the eBook

Citing links within the body of the eBook and knowing how much detail to include *in addition* to the URL is also a consideration.

This citation method from the University of Glasgow provides a helpful starting point:

Required information: Author's surname, Initial(s). Publication year. *Italicised title of website with only first letter of first word and proper nouns capitalised.* [Online]. [Accessed Date accessed]. Available from: URL

OR

Company name. Publication year. *Italicised title of website with only first letter of first word and proper nouns capitalised.* [Online]. [Accessed Date accessed]. Available from: URL

Example: National Library of Scotland. 2020. *Bàird Ghàidhlig na Ceapaich/Gaelic Bards of Keppoc.* [Online]. [Accessed 30 June 2020]. Available from: <https://digital.nls.uk/learning/gaelic-bards/>

If you are referencing a specific section of a website then the format is similar to the 'Journal Article' style.

Required information: Author's surname, Initial(s) (or company name). Publication year. Webpage title. *Italicised title of website with only first letter of first word and proper nouns capitalised.* [Online]. [Accessed Date accessed]. Available from: URL

Example: Higley, S. 2007. Preiddiau Annwn: The Spoils of Annwn. *The Camelot Project.* [Online]. [Accessed 30 June 2020]. Available at: <https://d.lib.rochester.edu/camelot/text/preiddeu-annwn>

Example: Alexander, M. and Kay, C. 2020. Facts and Figures. *About the Historical Thesaurus of English.* [Online]. [Accessed 28 October 2020]. Available <https://ht.ac.uk/facts-and-figures/>

Figure 1: web citation guidance, taken from <https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/library/referencing/harvard/#harvardreferencelistexamples,websites> [accessed 01 April 2026]

Individual publishers may have their own guidance on this, which could be discipline-specific – reach out for guidance.

The key thing is to clearly **document the URL of the information**, and to **consistently do so**. With this, and assuming the link breaks at some point, future users will at least have a chance of knowing where this information was originally located and may even be able to find a copy from existing web archive collections. In this case, it's possible to view the original URL text as 'preservation metadata' for future findability and access.²⁹

Best practice: cite to a web archive URL

The best link of all to cite to for critical information is a **web archive URL** of the resource, available and accessible from a reputable long-term, public access, not-for-profit web archive. These are listed in Appendix A, and helpful advice on how to cite web archive URLs is available ([Internet Archive](#)). Not only will this URL have, in principle, a greater resilience to link rot than a live URL, Web Archive URL's content are also frozen and fixed in time. In other words, the content in an archived webpage will not change or be updated, unlike web content, making this the number one tool to offset the more complex threat of content drift, we explored in section 2.2.

Checklist for publishers

For publishers who stand in line to receive manuscripts for edit and publication, it may be appropriate to check the condition of outbound links within the eBook when it arrives. Methodology for this may be dictated by the file format that the eBook is stored within. Here are some options:

²⁹ For more details on preservation metadata see, DPC Handbook, 'Metadata and documentation', available at <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/organisational-activities/metadata-and-documentation> [accessed 01 April 2026]

- MS Word files do not have an automatic function for checking links within them, but guidance is available for carrying this out manually (Lynn, [2022](#)).
- Adobe Acrobat Pro can be used to check links with PDFs, but it is recognised that this software would incur cost. Other at-cost options are available.³⁰
- Free open-source options are available, but these should be handled with caution and only used when adequate trust can be established, or in an isolated environment to prevent malware entering systems.³¹
- Other link checking opensource tools are listed within the IIPC's 'awesome web archiving' tools directory ([IIPC](#)).
- A final example relates to a Wordpress application which automatically scans Wordpress websites for outbound links and replaces these with archive links from the Internet Archive.³²
- In general, it is likely that these tools will work more easily and effectively with HTML eBooks than PDF.

Checklist for collecting repositories

For collecting repositories who will receive and preserve these works, perhaps indefinitely, they are likely to still acquire eBooks which harbour the risk of link rot. When planning what action to take against this, refer back to your operational policies, procedure and capabilities in determining next steps, for example:

- Do you have the time and resource to do any forensic work relating to link rot, or will it be a case of just receiving these and documenting this information within your collection management system?
- Does your collecting policy cover 'at-risk' content (such as hyperlinks) which may be useful for advocating for additional preservation effort?
- Does your organisation keep its own web archive, or have peer connections to web archiving institutions who could lend further support and advice?

Consider these questions against the link checking options for Publishers outlined above in determining what level of checks and actions to take.

Step 3 – Describe more, bolster accessibility

Potential cost rating: ££

³⁰ PowerMapper Website Link Checker Tool purports to be able to scan PDFs and Office documents for links. See <https://www.powermapper.com/products/sortsite/ads/links-link-checker/> [accessed 02 April 2026]

³¹ E.g. 'LinkDoc' from Peacock Media, available at <https://peacockmedia.software/mac/linkdoc/> [accessed 02 April 2026]

³² <https://wordpress.org/plugins/internet-archive-wayback-machine-link-fixer/> [accessed 02 April 2026]

Choosing links which have resilient design and following good practice in citing the original URL of a link are good steps towards better link resilience. One final step will strengthen this mission, and, in turn, enhance the overall accessibility of the eBook.

For critical and important links, it is worth documenting – in as much detail as possible – a description of the link’s content, context and structure. Ideally this could be documented within the body of the eBook itself, but a simple accompanying metadata file such as a .csv would do. This accompanying file could be submitted as part of the package of information for publication, and/or be linked to from the publication’s website over time. How much detail or descriptive content that can be provided is a resourcing question for the stakeholders to consider. This may be a manual endeavour at first, but it is also conceivable to see a role for AI-summarizer tools here, which could save time in generating a summary text for input into the body of the eBook.³³ However, doing *anything* in this step will almost certainly be a cheaper method than having to attempt the (not guaranteed) repair of link rot later down the line. Even a very simple line or two on the context, content and structure of the web resource, with a small number of accompanying screenshot images, becomes invaluable descriptive metadata.

This task is even more important to multimedia and audio-visual content being linked into eBooks from external sources. We have already discussed how it may be advantageous to package the associated files for this content as part of the eBook itself, but this may not be possible, especially if the files are held by a third party. A description of what this content is – to include transcripts, for example, or alt-text for embedded image files – will provide some level of resilience if these links break over time, or cannot be displayed. This approach might not work in all cases, especially for larger files or for highly complex content → refer to step 5 for further advice.

This additional descriptive work, and other steps above, intrinsically bolster the overall accessibility of the eBook – both for humans (users) and for machines (web crawlers). For authors, this can only be a positive thing: not only does this help strengthen the preservation of the work for the future, it also enhances the chances of the book reaching as wide an audience as possible right now. COPIM and OBF have created rich resources in understanding and applying accessibility into eBook production (COPIM, [2026](#)).

Checklist for authors

- Given you know the eBook’s link structure and content more than anyone, document as much description as you can.
- Use the points in Step 3 to consider where and how best to apply

Checklist for publishers

- Have a vested interest in ensuring that links with the eBook are at least listed and/or well described.

³³ Current tools include Adobe’s PDF Summarizer, and Microsoft 365’s AI Article Summarizer. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/word/ai-summarizer> and <https://www.adobe.com/uk/acrobat/online/ai-summary-generator.html?> [both accessed 01 April 2026]

- Collaborative working and/or workflows could be developed with authors to support this work.

Checklist for collecting repositories

- As part of the acquisition and cataloguing workflow, it may be appropriate to create short descriptions of each cited URL, especially for higher value content.
- The use of AI summarizer tools could be considered here.

Step 4 – Archive your URLs

Potential cost rating: ££-£££

If a web archive URL for an outbound link containing critical information for an eBook is not available, then it is advised that a copy is created by any one of the stakeholders to eBook preservation. Earlier in this report we observed the many types of web archiving services and tools which can be used to archive content.

For those who can do so, there are multiple opensource tools available, which can be used to capture, preserve and make available a local copy of websites ([IIPC](#)). However, developer skills are certainly not essential to getting into web archiving, and there are various free or low-cost services which can be used instead and which require little technical expertise. Two in particular are highlighted here.

Internet Archive Save Page Now

This free service provides a quick and easy way to have a capture made of a single URL:

Figure 2: WayBack Machine Homepage, indicating SavePageNow feature

Limited to a single page at a time, with a means to almost immediately render the contents of the capture for access and QA (along with a rewritten web archive URL) Save Page Now is an indispensable tool. There are now further options to sign up, and crucially, save a copy of the archived content in WACZ format – a recognised file format for long-term preservation of web pages. This copy in WACZ could be packaged as part of the eBook, removing the dependency on the Internet Archive itself for long term access to this copy. See this excellent tutorial from Aarhus university for more details: [Internet Archive Save Page Now](#).

ArchiveWeb.Page

For more dynamic pages, or to archive a group of pages from within a website e.g. a carousel of images or a set of paginated pages in succession, ArchiveWeb.Page provides an effective option. Note that pages archived in this way will not become publicly available: the model is designed to create copies of an archived website either in WACZ or in WARC, but which can then be viewed within the user account profile or replayed through associated replay software.

For screenshots and a guide to using ArchiveWeb.Page, see this guide from Lakehead University: <https://libguides.lakeheadu.ca/c.php?g=734257&p=5282156>

If it is viable, and if the content is of critical value, it may be worth considering making web archive copies of the link in question from both of the providers listed above, and possibly others. Multiple

copies and additional redundancy are further defences against link rot, though naturally the more copies which are kept, the greater the long-term preservation overhead will be.

Checklist for authors

- Following the informational value appraisal rating – critical or important, look to make at least one, possibly more copies of this content.
- Either use the newly generated web archive URL for citation purposes, or package the resulting WACZ/WARC file as part of the eBook.
- Reach out to your publisher to discuss further acquisition of this.

Checklist for publishers

- Given the scale and labour involved, this step may be too difficult to effect manually.
- Engagement with authors could support a joined up workflow, though it is also noted that tools exist for certain platforms that allow for auto-detecting and web archive URL generation in one action: <https://wordpress.org/plugins/internet-archive-wayback-machine-link-fixer/>.

Checklist for collecting repositories

- With longer-term preservation in mind, this step may be worth investing in, especially if a tool like the WordPress link auto-checker could be employed.
- Offsetting link rot for the repository at this stage will be cheaper than trying to fix a broken link after the fact.

Step 5 – Monitor your URLs, enact digital archaeology

Potential cost rating: ££

This step would only affect the part of the eBook lifecycle once the book itself is published and/or collected by a collecting repository. By this point, the design is complete, and whatever ‘changes’ can be effected on the eBook – whether for preservation, access, or other – will ultimately be dictated by policies at these respective institutions e.g. preservation policy and actions, revision policies, etc.

As has been made clear in this report, and even where resilience is built into URLs, outage and link rot still occurs, especially as the links age.³⁴ For that reason, it is good practice for the keepers of these completed books – be that the publisher or collecting repository, to maintain oversight of whether links within eBooks are still intact.

³⁴ Zhou et al. lays out analysis which links decaying rapidly in the following order: i) older publications ii) longer links, deeper within sites iii) articles which have not been heavily cited within high impact journals (Zhou et al., [2015](#), p.236)

Checklist for publishers and collecting repositories

- If the eBook is available online, the simplest means to carry out this check would be to employ one of the link checking tools available on the IIPC Awesome Web Archiving List – though note that some of these available as Google Chrome extensions appear to no longer be supported.
- These tools tend to work better with HTML, rather than PDF, Word and other proprietary formats.
- If a broken link *is* found within an eBook, then it is case of carrying out some ‘digital archaeology’ to see whether an archived link can be founded and highlighted to users. On how this is presented to users, ‘tombstone’ page design – for pages which are no longer live - may be informative. See this example: <http://www.dpoc.ac.uk/> [accessed 29 April 2026]
- The web archives listed in Appendix A would be the first resources to turn to for this.
- Sadly, with the demise of the Memento TimeTravel service, there is not a quick and easy way to query the global web archive collection to see if a copy of a particular site exists within a particular collection. For stakeholders comfortable with working with command line tools, Memgator may be one option to consider.³⁵

Summary of recommendations in this section

The tiered approach in Steps 1 to 5 to mitigating link rot as laid out in this section is summarized in the table below:

	Critical links	Important links	Non-important links
Should links remain in situ within the eBook?	Yes, but augment with web archive URL	Yes, but augment with web archive URL if available	Yes/No – see Step 1 for further guidance
If possible, should available files be packaged and preserved?	Yes	Possibly – assess value and resourcing	No
Add descriptive metadata?	Yes – as much as possible, total content if possible	Yes – as much as possible	If resource permits, but keep minimal
Create a web archive copy for online access?	Yes – ArchivePage and Browsertrix	Yes – ArchivePage, Browsertrix if necessary	No
Create a WARC or WACZ file for offline access?	Yes – SavePageNow and Browsertrix	Possibly – assess value and resourcing	No
Monitor links over time?	Yes	Yes	No

³⁵ <https://github.com/oduwsdl/MemGator> Other similar Memento aggregator tools are listed as ‘in development’ on the IIPC Awesome Web Archiving List [accessed 02 April 2026]

Conclusion

Digital preservation is all about working to ensure that we design and implement policies and procedures that will allow us to safeguard the digital content to which we are responsible; and be in a position to hand over that responsibility to the next generation.

It is impossible for us to know, without the aid of a crystal ball, whether the links we use to connect information for the understanding and enjoyment of our society will last. We have no idea how the Web will change next. At a time when AI and emerging technologies are seemingly making us less inclined to fully understand the provenance of what we are reading and at a time when so much Web content is consumed via apps, rather than web browsers with fully transparent URL address bars, will future generations even understand what a URL actually means? Only the next generation will truly be able to answer that question.

All we can do is work within the context that we know. This Report has spelled out that the current Web is flimsy, it is forgetful, it is frustrating. Any eBook which is fully reliant on the Web for its context, content and structure will unfortunately harbour the same characteristics.

But the Web is also a phenomenal tool to be exploited, to connect ideas, perspectives and learnings from across the World into the palm of our hand, or the screen of our study. Due to that, it is inevitable that the design of eBooks will continue to harness and rely on the power of the web as a source of networked information.

A new era of creative writing and intellectual expression feels upon us. But link rot may indeed get worse. As this Report has documented, the best ways for eBook stakeholders to mitigate against this threat is to:

- Think before you link, and determine acceptable loss
- Cite to resilient links
- Describe more, bolster accessibility
- Archive your URLs
- Monitor your URLs, enact digital archaeology

It is hoped that the contextual framework, articulation of risk, and description of each mitigation step within this Report, will act as a small contribution to the wider global mission of eBook preservation mission, for the benefit of future generations.

Looking ahead, it's worth considering whether the community could continue this work by designing practical, collective solutions, through further collaboration. Ideas might include:

- Scope to produce a platform-agnostic, community supported tool that could check any eBook – or digital document – for links, and fabricate a listing of equivalent web archive URLs.

- Building on guidance laid out in Step 2, engage the owners of large academic referencing models such as the Chicago Manual of Style, the APA Style, and Harvard on link rot and how web archive URL referencing could practically and easily help.³⁶
- Consider whether robust link citation could be offered as a shared service for the common good across the academic sector.

The DPC stands ready to offer any support and forum for dialogue on these matters.

³⁶ See https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/tools_citationguide.html; <https://apastyle.apa.org/>; <https://www.citethemrightonline.com/category-list?docid=CTRHarvard> [all accessed 29 April 2026]

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Appendix A: Openly Accessible Web Archives List

Open access English-language web archives to check for archived content include:

- Australian web archive (Trove): <https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/collection>
- EU Web Archive <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/euwebarchive>
- Government of Canada Web Archive <https://webarchiveweb.bac-lac.canada.ca/>
- Internet Archive <https://archive.org/>
- Library of Congress <https://www.loc.gov/web-archives/>
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- New Zealand Web Archive: <https://natlib.govt.nz/collections/a-z/new-zealand-web-archive>
- Public Record Office of Northern Ireland <https://webarchive.proni.gov.uk/#/>
- UK Web Archive (when restored) <https://www.webarchive.org.uk/>
- UK Government Web Archive <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/webarchive/>
- Web Archive Singapore: <https://eresources.nlb.gov.sg/webarchives/landing-page>

There are many, many other publicly available web archives – covering private, higher education, and public organisations - available to access. The IIPC membership list illustrates how this mission is being led across the world by numerous institutions: <https://netpreserve.org/about-us/members/> and many collections are available to access on platforms such as <https://archive-it.org/>.

The IIPC website is a great source for further information on developments and the release of new collections in this area: <https://netpreserve.org/>.